

Source: Amini, L., [Soudi, M. R.](#), Saboora, A., & Mobasheri, H. (2018). Effect of essential oil from *Zataria multiflora* on local strains of *Xanthomonas campestris*: An efficient antimicrobial agent for decontamination of seeds of *Brassica oleracea* var. capitata. *Scientia horticultrae*, 236, 256-264, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2018.03.046>

Effect of essential oil from *Zataria multiflora* on local strains of *Xanthomonas campestris*: An efficient antimicrobial agent for decontamination of seeds of *Brassica oleracea* var. capitata

Leila Amini^a, [Mohammad Reza Soudi](#)^a, Azra Saboora^b, Hamid Mobasheri^{c,d}

^aDepartment of Microbiology, Faculty of Sciences, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

^bDepartment of Botany, Faculty of Sciences, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

^cInstitute of Biochemistry and Biophysics (IBB), University of Tehran, Tehran, Iran

^dBiomaterials Research Center (BRC), University of Tehran, Tehran, Iran

ABSTRACT

In this study, the effect of the essential oil of *Zataria multiflora* was examined against the local strains of *Xanthomonas campestris* isolated from the soil. The pathogenicity of the bacteria was confirmed using seedlings on culture media under sterile conditions.

The minimum inhibitory and bactericidal concentrations of *Zataria multiflora* essential oil and two main components (thymol and carvacrol) were evaluated by the microdilution method in microtiter plates. The morphology of the surface of the seeds and characteristics of the grooves were studied by scanning electron microscopy. Hermetic effect of the essential oil and antimicrobial activity of the solvent on *X. campestris* were evaluated.

Minimum inhibitory and bactericidal concentrations of *Zataria multiflora* essential oil were 231.8 and 463.5 µg/mL, respectively. The viability of *X. campestris* in Yeast Malt Broth was reduced by 100% in the presence of *Zataria multiflora* essential oil (231.8 µg/mL), while, the seeds contaminated with the same count of *X. campestris* were disinfected at higher concentration of *Zataria multiflora* essential oil (463.5 µg/mL). Killing of *X. campestris* cells adhered to the seeds with uneven surface and deep grooves required greater concentrations of the essential oil. The impregnation of the seeds in the essential oil at 463.5 µg/mL showed that a 2-h exposure period causes the least possible damage to the seedlings and is sufficient to prevent the occurrence of the disease caused by *X. campestris* in *Brassica oleracea*.

Keywords: *Brassica oleracea* var. capitata, Essential oil, Phytopathogen, Seed decontamination, *Xanthomonas campestris*, *Zataria multiflora*